

InterAcción y Perspectiv

Revista de Trabajo Social

ISSN 2244-808X
D.L. pp 201002Z43506

Octubre-diciembre 2024
Vol. 14 No. 3

Universidad del Zulia
Facultad de Ciencias Jurídicas y Políticas
Centro de Investigaciones en Trabajo Social

Interacción y Perspectiva
Revista de Trabajo Social
Vol. 14 N°3 647-660 pp.
Octubre-diciembre

Dep. Legal pp 201002Z43506
ISSN 2244-808X
Copyright © 2024

ARTÍCULO DE INVESTIGACIÓN

Respuestas emocionales a la corrupción en diversos sectores de la sociedad: contenido y dinámica

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11154833>

Svetlana Dzhanyan *, Darya Gvozdeva **, Ludmila Gabdulina***, Ekaterina
Belova****, Alina Kim*****

Resumen

Uno de los obstáculos a la lucha contra la corrupción son las actitudes de la población hacia ella y la tolerancia de tales actitudes entre determinados segmentos de la población. Este artículo analiza el contenido (características y modalidad) y la dinámica de las reacciones emocionales a la corrupción en los ámbitos de la educación, la carrera, la vida profesional, y la sociedad entre los individuos dentro del espectro de la universidad al trabajo, en relación con sus correspondientes actitudes hacia la corrupción. Se aplicaron encuestas, análisis de contenido y pruebas (Escala de Emociones Diferenciales de Izard. Los resultados indican que dentro del espectro universidad-trabajo, las actitudes predominantes hacia la corrupción son las relaciones de Transacción Económica Empresarial y Valor Instrumental. Independientemente del tipo de actitud, la corrupción como fenómeno social suscita emociones negativas entre todos los participantes (excepto para los estudiantes que muestran neutralidad hacia la corrupción percibida como un valor Instrumental) y específicamente en los campos de carrera y profesional entre los encuestados que trabajan. La naturaleza de las emociones fluctúa en función de la actitud hacia la corrupción, su contexto de manifestación y el estatus de los encuestados. Se concluye que dentro del espectro que va de la universidad al trabajo, la dinámica de las respuestas emocionales de los encuestados a la corrupción en la educación, la carrera y los campos profesionales, y en la sociedad en general, está condicionada por su actitud hacia la corrupción, manifestándose en reacciones emocionales específicas, cambios en la naturaleza y modalidad de las emociones.

Palabras clave: percepción de la corrupción, tolerancia actitudinal, espectro universidad-trabajo, corrupción en el sector educativo, escala de emociones diferenciales, análisis de contenido.

Abstract

Emotional responses to corruption across various sectors of society: content and dynamics

One of the obstacles to the fight against corruption is the attitudes of the population towards it and the tolerance of such attitudes among certain segments of the population.

This article analyzes the content (characteristics and modality) and dynamics of emotional reactions to corruption in education, career, professional life, and society among individuals within the university-to-work spectrum, in relation to their corresponding attitudes toward corruption. Surveys, content analysis and tests were applied (Izard's Differential Emotions Scale). The results indicate that within the university-work spectrum, the predominant attitudes towards corruption are the relationships of Business Economic Transaction and Instrumental Value. Regardless of the type of attitude, corruption as a social phenomenon elicits negative emotions among all participants (except for students who show neutrality towards corruption perceived as an instrumental value) and specifically in the career and professional fields among working respondents. The nature of emotions fluctuates depending on the attitude towards corruption, its context of manifestation, and the status of the respondents. It is concluded that within the spectrum that goes from university to work, the dynamics of respondents' emotional responses to corruption in education, career and professional fields, and in society in general, is conditioned by their attitude towards corruption, manifesting itself in specific emotional reactions, changes in the nature and modality of emotions.

Keywords: corruption perception, attitudinal tolerance, university-to-work spectrum, education sector corruption, differential emotions scale, content analysis.

Recibido: 29/02/2024 Aceptado: 22/04/2024

* La Universidad Federal del Sur, Academia de Psicología y Pedagogía, Rostov del Don, Rusia. ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1743-5751> . E-mail: swetdjan@sfedu.ru

** La Universidad Federal del Sur, Academia de Psicología y Pedagogía, Rostov del Don, Rusia. ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3577-7760> . E-mail: gvozdeva@sfedu.ru

*** La Universidad Federal del Sur, Academia de Psicología y Pedagogía, Rostov del Don, Rusia. ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1143-6470> . E-mail: gal@sfedu.ru

**** La Universidad Federal del Sur, Academia de Psicología y Pedagogía, Rostov del Don, Rusia. ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0683-137X> . E-mail: evprokopeva@sfedu.ru

***** La Universidad Federal del Sur, Academia de Psicología y Pedagogía, Rostov del Don, Rusia. ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0004-4899-9770> . E-mail: alink@sfedu.ru

1. Introduction

One of significant obstacles to the struggle against corruption is the specific content of attitudes towards it among the population as a whole and the tolerance of such attitude among a portion of the population.

According to the vast majority of works, the objective side of the relationship under study designated as corruption integrates its various manifestations. The literature discusses the criteria for identifying types and forms of corruption, along with an indication of the consequences for subjects of different scales (Gavelis, 2012; Fan, 2019; Abdulla, 2021). The types and forms of corruption that are regarded by researchers as one of the differentiating factors in the perception and attitude towards corruption among the population (Fan, 2019). In the minds of citizens, corruption acts as an acceptable and convenient mechanism for social life and solving personal problems (Kondrashov, 2016), a forced response to objective circumstances, a specific value (Nikolaev, 2019). These positions testify to the relevance of considering the

psychological attitude to corruption as a value-semantic (goal-meaning) attitude, in which corruption comprehended by the subject as a tool in achieving their goals and satisfying their needs.

Attitudes towards corruption includes cognitive, emotional, behavioral components (Harris & Bastedo, 2011; Harris & van der Merwe, 2012; Abun et al., 2020; Zhuravlev & Kitova, 2022). The content of specific attitude lies not only in their substantive objective content, but in the significance of the objective for the subject (Karpova et al., 2020). With this in mind, we included people's interpretations of corruption and its functions in the life of a particular individual in the content of the cognitive component of the value-semantic attitude to corruption. In this regard, the cognitive component is decisive for designating the type and subsequent analysis of the value-semantic attitude to corruption.

The conative component of the attitude is expressed in motives and attitudes arising from them, readiness to act one way or another with the object (Karpova et al., 2020), including causes (Prasad et al., 2019), situational factors (Fischer et al., 2014), justification (Harris & van der Merwe, 2012; McGee et al., 2015; Gutiérrez et al., 2017; Zhuravlev & Kitova, 2022) of corruption manifestations. The content of this component is the most relevant in terms of predicting the actual corrupt behavior in citizens with different attitudes towards corruption. However, the results of studying the corruption situation (D' Agostino & Pieroni, 2019; Abun et al., 2020; Parra et al., 2021; Tanner et al., 2022) do not allow a clear prediction of the real behavior of subjects in a real corruption situation. Along with this, the majority of researchers from various branches of science state a significant weight of the psychological characteristics of subjects in a number of causes of corruption (Fan, 2019; Li et al., 2019; De Waele et al., 2021), therefore we included the factors of giving and receiving a bribe as well as respondents' assessments of the personality traits of a corrupting and a corrupted individual in the content of the conative component.

The content of the emotional-evaluative component of the attitude under discussion, which is represented by a verbal version of the respondents' perceived emotions and assessments of corruption, is of particular interest in connection with the subject of this study (Güvenli & Sanyal, 2012; Harris & van der Merwe, 2012; Gutiérrez et al., 2017). Emotions towards corruption among ordinary citizens are recorded in a wide range of experiences different in modality and sign: indifference, apathy (Fan, 2019), negative feelings (Abun et al., 2020; Zhuravlev & Kitova, 2022) positive emotions from participation in corrupt exchanges (Zhuravlev & Kitova, 2022). There is a connection between the modality of emotions and the type of corruption (top or bottom) (Fan, 2019) status of corrupt individuals (Fan, 2019), anti-corruption measures (Zhuravlev & Kitova, 2022) the stage of conformation to corrupt behavior. It is less often noted that the attitude towards corruption is differentiated according to its sign depending on the field of life in which corruption takes place (Nikolaev, 2019).

The verbal version of emotional assessment of corruption presented by the respondent reflects the result of their awareness of their own experience. In turn, a

person's awareness of their own experience is based on the correlation of this experience with the object that causes it, and with the consequences for the person (Yurov, 2015). Based on this, we considered the content of emotional-evaluative component as covering not only emotions towards corruption, but also assessments of its consequences for subjects of various scales (state, social groups, a particular individual) and its countermeasures. In this article we focused on the analysis of only the emotional experiences that people experience towards corruption in various fields of life. Here, it is relevant to obtain an answer to the question about the dynamics of emotional experiences in attitude to corruption. The emotional component of a holistic attitude is the first step towards changing attitudes, which predetermines research interest in emotional assessments of corruption.

The dynamics of attitudes towards corruption recorded by researchers is manifested in an increase in the tolerance of said attitude (Vannovskaia, 2009) in feeling comfortable with a bribe in the process of perpetuating individual corrupt behaviour. The inconsistency of attitudes towards corruption is pointed out, which consists in the inconsistency of the content of the cognitive and emotional components.

Methodically, the solution to the issue of dynamics of the emotional response to corruption is to involve methods of longitudinal or transverse sections. It is obvious that the latter is possible provided that the type of relation being measured is constant. Such constancy is fixed by researchers who use tolerance as a criterion for typology of attitudes. Our studies have established the presence of similar types (in terms of the content of the cognitive component) of attitudes among schoolchildren, college students, students, and working subjects. This allows to establish the characteristics and dynamics of emotional experiences towards corruption in specific areas of life among respondents who differ in status and age characteristics, but demonstrate a similar type of value-semantic attitude towards corruption. Analysis of the content of the emotional response should include not only the sign, but also the phenomenology of the modality of emotions. To solve this problem, a study was undertaken aimed at establishing the content (sign and modality) and the dynamics of emotional experiences towards corruption in different areas of life among students and working subjects with similar types of value-semantic attitudes towards corruption.

2. Materials and methods

Participants included 120 university students aged 19-26, 102 young working adults aged 22-31, and 116 mature working adults aged 34-59, all employed in a variety of professions in the southern region of the Russian Federation.

The study utilized several measures to examine the components of attitudes toward corruption. These included a survey with a questionnaire designed to explore the content of attitudes toward corruption, content analysis of the questionnaire's open-ended

questions, testing using the Scale of Differential Emotions (Izard, 2010), the cross-sectional method, and statistical data analysis techniques.

In our previous publications, we described a methodological procedure for establishing types of attitudes towards corruption: pilot coding of respondents' answers, expert assessment of the adequacy of the choice of category indicators and a measure of consistency of these assessments (Dzhaneryan et al., 2016; Dzhaneryan & Gvozdeva, 2020). The relative frequency of occurrence of a category was taken as a quantitative unit of content analysis, each of which reflected the content of components of attitudes towards corruption (Dzhaneryan et al., 2016).

Results of the content-analytical processing were reflected in the content-semantic interpretations of corruption and its functions - in the cognitive component, which was considered as paramount for the designation and subsequent analysis of the value-semantic attitude towards corruption.

Based on the results of the factor analysis of indicators denoting the definitions of corruption, and on the basis of determining the dominant individual factor assessment for each respondent, groups of students, working respondents, as subjects of one or another type of attitude towards corruption were identified. The types of their attitude were identified: Illegal act (29.6% of mature working respondents); Business economic transaction (63.3% of students; 67.5% of young and 34.7% of mature working respondents); Instrumental value (36.7% of students, 32.5% of young and 35.6% of mature working respondents). In the university-work range, the through types are the Business Economic Transaction and Instrumental Value attitudes.

In relation to the Business Economic Transaction, corruption is understood by the respondents as social interaction or the exchange of services and the corresponding reward for it; in relation to the Instrumental Value - as a universal means of satisfying various scarce human needs. Here we focused on establishing the emotional experiences that accompany the knowledge of respondents about the prevalence of corruption in the areas of education, professional career, and society as a whole. Respondents assessed the frequency of corruption in each of these areas on a 10-point scale (1 point - does not occur at all, 10 points - occurs to the greatest extent) while answering the question of the questionnaire: "To what extent is corruption widespread in each of the areas of life?". The emotional response of a respondent to information about the facts of corruption was recorded using the Scale of Differential Emotions, which allows for describing each of the fundamental emotions using a list of adjectives. The instruction asked the respondent to assess the presence of each of the emotions corresponding to their current emotional response to information about the corruption manifestation event. The individual emotional response was calculated based on the dominance of one or another fundamental emotion in the respondent in response to the fact of corruption in various fields of public life that became known to them. Each of the fundamental emotions is characterized by the specifics of phenomenology and behavioural

pattern; the universality of expression, interpretation and understanding by people; has a motivational potential and activity directed at the cause of emotions (interest,

surprise, disgust, contempt, anger) or its consequences in the form of actualization of the subject's self-consciousness (shame, guilt, grief) (Izard, 2010). Then, multiple linear regression analysis was carried out, where the dependent variable was the respondent's assessment of the frequency of corruption in a particular area of life, and independent variables were emotional experiences. The leading partial emotional experiences associated with respondents' awareness of the prevalence of corruption in a particular area of life were determined by the maximum values of the standardized coefficient of regression beta.

Statistical processing of the results was carried out using multiple linear regression analysis, descriptive statistics, quartile procedures, binomial criteria. Regression analysis, as well as checking the assumptions about the normality of distributions, were performed in the Factor Analysis, Multiple Regression, Descriptive Statistics modules (Shapiro-Wilks' W-test, Kolmogorov-Smirnov normality test for general relations with adjusted probabilities for sample observations Lilliefors) of the Tibco statistica 13.3 software.

3. Results and discussion

Prevalence of corrupt practices

Respondents were quite aware of the prevalence of corrupt practices. Table 1 presents the results reflecting the distribution of respondents demonstrating grades of assessments - very low ($X < 4.25$), low ($X \geq 4.25$ and $X < 6$), high ($X \geq 6$ and $X < 8$), very high ($X \geq 8$) as frequencies of corruption in different areas of life. The number of respondents in each of the groups assessing the severity of corrupt manifestations in the relevant area of life was taken as 100% (Table 1).

Table 1

Distribution of respondents' assessments (in %) of the frequency of corruption in education, career and professional fields, and in society as a whole

Respondents	Low and very low scores	High and very high scores
Education		
University students	19.92	80.09
Working individuals	52.74	47.25
Career and professional field		
University students	31.33	68.66
Working individuals	50.2	48.87
Society as a whole		
University students	49.03	50.95
Working individuals	52.66	47.29

Source: Conducted by the researchers

Firstly, students, compared with working respondents, gravitate toward high rates of corruption in education and the career and professional fields. The peak of high scores of the frequency of corruption is noted by students in the field of education. Secondly, students rate the frequency of corruption in education and career and professional fields higher than the frequency of corruption in society as a whole. In other words, already in the course of their education, the majority of students formed an idea of the high frequency of corruption not only in the area of occurrence that is relevant to them, but also in their future area of professional career.

The characteristics of respondents' emotional experiences regarding corruption in education, career and professional fields, in society as a whole were considered depending on the type of value-semantic attitude towards corruption.

Attitude towards corruption "Business Economic Transaction"

Thus, in the presence of the Business Economic Transaction attitude, the leading emotional experiences towards corruption in education were found only among adult working subjects - expressed interest (Table 2). Leading emotional experiences towards corruption in education among students and young working subjects have not been identified.

Table 2
Emotional experiences towards corruption in different areas of life among respondents who demonstrate their attitude to corruption as a Business Economic Transaction

Education	Career and professional field	Society as a whole
Students		
Unidentified	(R=0,604; p <0,0017) Interest (Beta= +0,263; p<0,05) Grief (Beta=-0,525; p<0,0031) Contempt (Beta=+0,614; p<0,0005)	(R=0,424; p<0,031) Fear (Beta= +0,766; p<0,009) Shame (Beta=-0.572; p<0.049)
Working individuals (ages 22 to 33)		
Unidentified	(R=0,509; p<0,0067) Anger (Beta=+0,509; p<0,0067)	(R=0,662; p<0,00098) Joy (Beta=+0,264; p<0,1) Contempt (Beta=+0,574; p<0,0016)
Working individuals (ages 31 to 59)		
(R=0,414; p<0,0011)	(R=0,466; p<0,00015)	(R=0,463; p<0,00017)

Interest (Beta=+0,401; p<0,00083) Fear (Beta=-0,322; p<0,0064)	Interest (Beta=+0,531; p<0,000036) Shame (Beta=-0,372; p<0,0057)	Anger (Beta=+0,571; p<0,000033) Shame (Beta=-0,315; p<0,017)
---	---	---

Notes: **R** is the coefficient of multiple linear regression; **Beta** is the standardized regression coefficient.

The leading emotional experience towards corruption in the career and professional fields in students is expressed contempt, in young working subjects - expressed anger, in mature working subjects - expressed interest. The peak of negative hostile experiences towards corruption in the career and professional fields takes place among students and working youth, which is confirmed by the modality of emotions of contempt and anger demonstrated by students and working youth, which are included in the so-called hostile triad consisting of disgust, contempt and anger (Izard, 2010). The leading emotional experience towards corruption in society is manifested in students in expressed fear, in young working respondents in expressed contempt, in mature working respondents in expressed anger.

Attitude towards corruption "Instrumental Value"

If the respondents have the "Instrumental Value" attitude, the leading emotional experience towards corruption in the field of education is low guilt among students, and pronounced guilt among adult working subjects. Young working subjects do not have leading emotional experiences about corruption in the field of education.

The leading emotional experiences towards corruption in the career and professional fields are pronounced fear in young working subjects, pronounced grief in mature working subjects. Students do not have leading emotional experiences towards corruption in the career and professional fields and in society as a whole (Table 3).

Table 3

Emotional experiences of the prevalence of corruption in different areas of life among respondents who demonstrate their attitude towards corruption as an Instrumental value

Education	Career and professional field	Society as a whole
Students		
(R=0,642; p<0,026) Anger (Beta=+0,583; p<0,024)	Unidentified	Unidentified

Shame (Beta=+1,005; p<0,03)		
Guilt (Beta=-1,529; p<0,005)		
Working individuals (ages 22 to 33)		
Unidentified	(R=0,974; p<0,019) Interest (Beta=-0,496; p<0,016) Grief (Beta=-1,398; p<0,0049) Disgust (Beta=1,19; p<0,0021) Contempt (Beta=-1,22; p<0,0045) Fear (Beta=+1,851; p<0,0039). Shame (Beta=+0,868; p<0,0083) Guilt (Beta=-0,698; p<0,012)	(R=0,894; p<0,0063) Joy (Beta=+0,825; p<0,021) Grief (Beta=+1,53; p<0,0023) Anger (Beta=-0,977; p<0,0062) Guilt (Beta=-1,01; p<0,0021)
Working individuals (ages 31 to 59)		
(R=0,303; p<0,028) Shame (Beta=-0,30; p<0,048) Guilt (Beta=+0,408; p<0,008)	(R=0,412; p<0,001) Grief (Beta=+0,374; p<0,0009). Shame (Beta=-0,275; p<0,013)	(R=0,643; p<0,00000) Grief (Beta=+0,381; p<0,00044) Disgust (Beta=+0,291; p<0,0047) Fear (Beta=+0,382; p<0,0012) Guilt (Beta=-0,416; p<0,00062)

Notes: **R** is the coefficient of multiple linear regression; **Beta** is the standardized regression coefficient.

The leading emotional experiences towards corruption in society were distributed as follows: students did not have such experiences, young working respondents had pronounced grief, and mature working respondents had pronounced grief and fear.

Discussion

Summarizing the results of the study leads to the conclusion that there is both invariance and variability of the sign of emotions shown by respondents in relation to corruption in a particular area of people's lives.

Firstly, negative experiences in all respondents (excluding students who demonstrate neutrality to corruption comprehended as an Instrumental value) are caused by corruption as a social phenomenon, and among young working respondents the cause is corruption in the career and professional fields. In other cases, the sign of emotions varies depending on the type of attitude towards corruption, the scope of its manifestation and the status of respondents. The positive interest in corruption in education and the career and professional fields among mature working subjects demonstrating the Business Economic Transaction attitude is noteworthy. The positive emotional response of mature working respondents reinforces their preconceived notions, and perhaps their direct experience that thanks to corruption, successful learning outcomes, finding a job, profitable career moves, etc. can be reliably, quickly, and effortlessly ensured. This experience or corrupt scenario can be passed on to the younger generation, thus creating a kind of corruption cycle.

Secondly, a neutral response to corruption in the areas of life under consideration takes place among young people and, in particular, among students. At the final stages of the university-work range, there is a pronounced emotional response, the sign of which is determined by the type of attitude of subjects to corruption.

Thirdly, in terms of content, such modalities as interest, surprise, disgust, anger are considered as feelings towards the drive that caused it, manifesting itself as a capture by the object (interest) (Izard, 2010), a desire to get away from the object (disgust), superiority over the object (contempt), the desire to attack the object as a source of anger. These emotions towards corruption are leading mainly among respondents (excluding students) demonstrating the type of attitude towards corruption as a Business Economic Transaction.

On the contrary, such modalities as fear, guilt, grief contribute to the actualization of a person's self-consciousness, manifesting themselves, respectively, as a premonition of complete vulnerability, insecurity (fear), as repentance, self-condemnation, lowering self-esteem (guilt), as an experience of discouragement, suffering (grief). Emotions of this kind directly reflect not so much the reaction to the fact of corruption as the reaction to the consequences for the subject. They are leading among respondents who demonstrate the type of attitude towards corruption as an Instrumental value.

Finally, from the point of view of intolerance of attitudes towards corruption, the respondents who implement the attitude towards corruption as a Business Economic Transaction are encouraging. Thus, contempt and anger are shown by students and young working respondents, respectively, towards corruption in the career and professional fields, and young and mature workers towards corruption in society as a whole.

Based on the results of the study, we can talk about the selective dynamics of the emotional response of respondents to corruption, which manifests itself in a particular area of life, depending on the type of their attitude towards corruption.

If corruption is comprehended as a Business Economic Transaction in education, then the shift in leading emotional experiences from the beginning to the end of the university-work range can be traced as a transition from a neutral response to positive (interest) emotions; if corruption is comprehended as an Instrumental value, then from avoiding negative (guilt) emotions to its actualization (guilt).

In the case of attitude towards corruption as a Business Economic Transaction in the career and professional fields, the shift in leading emotional experiences from the beginning to the end of the university-work range can be traced as a transition from pronounced negative (contempt) experiences to the actualization of positive (interest) experiences; in the case of attitude to corruption as an Instrumental value in the career and professional fields - as a shift from a neutral response to a negative (grief) experience.

If corruption is comprehended as a Business Economic Transaction in the society as a whole, then the shift of its leading emotional experiences from the beginning to the end of the university-work range manifests itself as a change in the modalities of negative emotions (fear, anger, respectively). If there is an attitude towards corruption as an Instrumental value, there is a shift from a neutral response to negative emotions (grief, fear).

4. Conclusion

The presence, sign and modality of the emotional response of subjects to corruption is determined by their status and the type of their attitude towards corruption. The obtained results lead to the conclusion that it is necessary to form specific anti-corruption psychological and pedagogical programs of work with the population, taking into account the type of attitude to corruption, the scope of its manifestation, the status of people. We believe that young respondents who experience negative emotions towards corruption are seriously interested in organizing an effective anti-corruption education system that would reveal possible measures to prevent corruption and also demonstrate the real results of their implementation.

Bibliographic references

- Abdulla, K. (2021). "Corrosive effects of corruption on human capital and aggregate productivity". **Kyklos**, 74 (4), 445-462. <https://doi.org/10.1111/kykl.12279>
- Abun, D., Encarnacion, M. J., Magallanes, T., & Lalaine, S. (2020). "Students' attitude toward corruption and their behavioural intention to corrupt or not to

- corrupt in the future: The Philippines' context". **Journal of the Social Sciences**, 23 (1), 78-98.
- d'Agostino, G., & Pieroni, L. (2019). "Modelling corruption perceptions: Evidence from eastern Europe and central Asian countries". **Social Indicators Research**, 142, 311-341. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11205-018-1886-3>
 - De Waele, L., Weißmüller, K. S., & van Witteloostuijn, A. (2021). "Bribery and the role of public service motivation and social value orientation: A multi-site experimental study in Belgium, Germany and the Netherlands". **Frontiers in Psychology**, 12, 655964. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.655964>
 - Dzhanyan, S. T., & Gvozdeva, D. I. (2020). **Soderzhaniye i sformirovannost' tipov tsennostno-smyslovogo otnosheniya k nizovoy korruptsii v forme vzyatochnichestva u gorodskoy uchashcheyasya molodezhi** [The content and formation of the types of value-semantic attitude to bottom corruption in the form of bribery among urban student youth]. Moscow: Publishing house "Znanie-M".
 - Dzhanyan, S. T., Gvozdeva, D. I., & Astafyeva, I. N. (2016). "Understanding of the causes of bribery by students with various types of attitude to bribery". **The Social Sciences**, 11 (S3), 6459-6464.
 - Fan, I. B. (2019). Korruptsiya kak problema politicheskoy antropologii [Corruption as a problem of political anthropology]. In: Rudenko, V. N. (Ed.) **Actual problems of scientific support of the state policy of the Russian Federation in the field of combating corruption: A collection of works on the results of the third all-Russian scientific conference with international participation, IPLUBRAS**, 26-27 October 2018, Ekaterinburg, Russia (pp. 349-368). Ekaterinburg: Institute of Philosophy and Law, Ural Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences. <https://doi.org/10.17506/articles.anticorruption.2018.349368>
 - Fischer, R., Ferreira, M. C., Milfont, T., & Pilati, R. (2014). "Culture of corruption? The effects of priming corruption images in a high corruption context". **Journal of Cross-Cultural Psychology**, 45 (10), 1594-1605. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022022114548874>
 - Gavelis, V. (2012). "An economic approach to corruption types". **Economics, Political Science**, 91, 4.
 - Gutiérrez, J. G., Saiz-Álvarez, J. M., & Ángel, G. (2017). "A cognitive, emotional and behavioral assessment of Colombian entrepreneurs' attitudes toward corruption". **Universidad & Empresa**, 19 (33), 9-51. <https://doi.org/10.12804/revistas.urosario.edu.co/empresa/a.4682>
 - Guvenli, T., & Sanyal, R. (2012). "Perception and understanding of bribery in international business". **Ethics and Behavior**, 22 (5), 333-348. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10508422.2012.706140>

- Harris, G., & van der Merwe, A. D. (2012). "The scope for mobilizing public opinion against corruption: The attitudes of Kwazulu-Natal university students". **South African Journal of Economic and Management Sciences**, 15 (3), a301. <https://doi.org/10.4102/sajems.v15i3.301>
- Harris, N. F., & Bastedo, M. N. (2011). Corruption at the top: Ethical dilemmas in college and university governance. In: Gallant, T. B. (Ed.) **Creating the ethical academy: A systems approach to understanding misconduct and empowering change in higher education**. New York: Routledge.
- Izard, C. E. (2010). "The many meanings/aspects of emotion: Definitions, functions, activation, and regulation". **Emotion Review**, 2 (4), 363-370. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1754073910374661>
- Karpova, E. B., Isurina, G. L., & Zhuravlev, A. L. (2020). "Psychology of relations by V. N. Miasishchev: Origins and contents". **Psikhologicheskii zhurnal**, 41 (2), 5-14. <https://doi.org/10.31857/S020595920008488-2>
- Kondrashov, P. N. (2016). "Dinamika zhiznennykh tsennostey podrostkov i problema korruptsii v postsovetsoy Rossii" ["Dynamics of vital values of adolescents and a problem of corruption in post-soviet Russia"]. **The Education and Science Journal**, 6, 22-41. <https://doi.org/10.17853/1994-5639-2016-6-22-41>
- Li, C., Liu, L., Zheng, W., Dang, J., & Liang, Y. (2019). "A clean self reduces bribery intent". **International Journal of Psychology**, 54 (2), 247-255. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ijop.12452>
- McGee, R. W., Benk, S., & Yüzbaşı, D. (2015). "Religion and ethical attitudes toward accepting a bribe: A comparative study". **Religions**, 6 (4), 1168-1181. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rel6041168>
- Nikolaev, S. M. (2019). "Modeling of cadets' preparation in educational establishments of higher education of the penitentiary system for anti-corruption activities". **Espacios**, 40 (29), 3.
- Parra, D., Muñoz-Herrera, M., & Palacio, L. A. (2021). "The limits of transparency in reducing corruption". **Journal of Behavioral and Experimental Economics**, 95 (C), 101762. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socec.2021.101762>
- Prasad, M., da Silva, M. B. M., & Nickow, A. (2019). "Approaches to corruption: A synthesis of the scholarship". **Studies in Comparative International Development**, 54 (1), 96-132. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12116-018-9275-0>
- Tanner, C., Linder, S., & Sohn, M. (2022). "Does moral commitment predict resistance to corruption? Experimental evidence from a bribery game". **Plos One**, 17 (1), e0262201. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0262201>
- Vannovskaia, O. V. (2009). "Problema korruptsii v psikhologicheskoy fenomenologii" ["The problem of corruption in psychological phenomenology"].

Bulletin of St. Petersburg University, 3 (2), 54-62 (2009).
<https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/problema-korrupsii-v-psihologicheskoy-fenomenologii/viewer>

- Yurov, I. A. (2015). "S.L. Rubinshteyn: Dialektiko-materialisticheskaya i gumanisticheskaya psikhologii" ["S.L. Rubinstein: Dialectical-materialistic and humanistic"]. **Psychologist**, 4, 37-84. <https://doi.org/10.7256/2409-8701.2015.4.15394>
- Zhuravlev, A. L., & Kitova, D. A. (2022). "The attitude of youth to corruption as a manifestation of the economic mentality of Russians". **Psychology and Law**, 12 (2), 178-193. <https://doi.org/10.17759/psylaw.2022120213>